

SUMEX DELIVERABLE D5.3

SUMMARY REPORT OF DIFFUSION WORKSHOP

Summary:

This report summarises the steps taken to organise the SUMEX Diffusion Workshop which was held on 5 September 2023 as a session of the World Resources Forum in Geneva, co-organised with the EU-funded projects CIRAN and RE-SOURCING. The report also details main outcomes with relevance for the project.

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This report summarises the steps taken to organise the SUMEX Diffusion Workshop, which was held on September the fifth 2023 as a session of the World Resources Forum in Geneva, co-organised with the EU-funded projects [CIRAN](#) and [RE-SOURCING](#). The report also details the main outcomes relevant to the project.

The session at the World Resources Forum used a high-level panel discussion format, and it was intitled “Balancing minerals extraction and nature protection: The implications of the EU Critical Raw Materials Act for Europe’s energy transition”. The organisation of the session presented an opportunity to collaborate with aligned EU-funded projects CIRAN and RE-SOURCING, both of which have connected objectives. The announcement of the European Commission’s Critical Raw Materials Act proposal provided a timely backdrop that generated visibility around raw materials topics relevant to SUMEX. With the Act sparking greater attention on securing raw material supply sustainably, the session created an impactful platform to highlight SUMEX objectives and outputs. Additionally, the World Resources Forum's offering of on-site and online attendance provided an ideal venue to maximise exposure for SUMEX among our target stakeholders.

The event aimed to establish a dialogue with different stakeholders on how to reach a balanced approach between the need for mineral raw materials and nature protection. The session allowed to highlight SUMEX project outputs as tools at the service of industry, permitting authorities and policy makers when it comes to striving for nature protection in the extractive sector.

In this context, the SUMEX toolkit, encompassing both a Massive Open Online Course and a Knowledge Repository, has been actively promoted as a compilation of best practice guidelines in this field. The SUMEX Sustainability Framework was prominently displayed on a banner close to the stage and has been introduced during the keynote speech of SUMEX coordinator Michael Tost as a roadmap allowing actors in the extractive industries to progressively advance from initial legal compliance requirements to an enhanced sustainability vision. Furthermore, all participants have been invited to join the SUMEX Community of Practice, which aims to offer a virtual forum for ongoing discussions around sustainable extractive practices during and beyond the project’s funding period.

1 INTRODUCTION

The SUMEX Diffusion Workshop was organised as a high-level panel discussion session at the 2023 World Resources Forum in Geneva. Named "Balancing minerals extraction and nature protection: The implications of the EU Critical Raw Materials Act for Europe's energy transition", the event took place on September the fifth. By leveraging the World Resources Forum platform and online streaming, the discussion provided an impactful venue to disseminate SUMEX project outputs, key findings and increase visibility among target stakeholders.

The ambition of SUMEX (Sustainable Management in Extractive industries) is to promote sustainability in the European extractive sector. For this, the [SUMEX sustainability framework](#) has been established, with the involvement of stakeholders from civil society, academia, industry and government backgrounds from all across the EU. In addition to this framework, SUMEX developed a digital toolkit consisting of a [Knowledge Repository](#) and a [Massive Open Online Course](#) (MOOC). The Knowledge Repository is an open-access toolkit of good practices around sustainability in the extractive sector; the MOOC is a six-week online course that addresses the most pressing issues and practical challenges of sustainable management in the extractive sector faced by decision-makers.

The SUMEX framework and toolkit were actively promoted throughout the event. A banner displaying the sustainability framework was displayed close to the stage and flyers about the toolkit were distributed to all participants. These outputs were also explicitly introduced by SUMEX coordinator Michael Tost during his keynote speech. In conclusion both on-site and online participants were invited to join the [SUMEX Community of Practice](#), which serves as a virtual forum on LinkedIn, fostering continuous discussions on sustainable management within the extractive industries, both during and beyond the project's funding period.

2 PREPARATORY PHASE

To strategically align with the overarching goals of the SUMEX Diffusion Workshop, we focused on leveraging three critical considerations. First and foremost, the workshop was timed to coincide with a significant major event, thereby ensuring heightened visibility within the target audience. Secondly, a deliberate effort was made to tether the workshop to the prevailing policy landscape of the European Union, firmly anchoring it within the current EU policy context. Lastly, a concerted endeavour was made to foster collaborative connections by creating synergies with other EU-funded projects, particularly with CIRAN (initiated in January 2023) and RE-SOURCING (slated for conclusion in October 2023). This approach not only fortified the workshop's objectives but also established valuable linkages with projects sharing complementary aims.

CIRAN

The aim of CIRAN is to reconcile two, sometimes conflicting, societal objectives and needs: protecting environmentally sensitive areas and increasing socio-economic resilience. In an era of uncertainty and demanding outcomes for people and government, CIRAN will deliver a functional solution to resolve such conflicting interests with the help of endorsed 'social contract' models.

More information: <https://ciranproject.eu/>

RE-SOURCING Project

RE-SOURCING is an EU-funded Multi-Stakeholder Platform that is actively contributing to Responsible Sourcing of raw materials along and across global mineral value chains. It strives to promote both strategic agenda setting and coherent application of practices for Responsible Sourcing.

More information: <https://re-sourcing.eu/>

The World Resources Forum, a major event in the field of sustainable resource management, provided an ideal platform to maximise SUMEX's visibility offering both on-site and online attendance options.

The announcement of the European Commission's Critical Raw Materials Act proposal provided a timely backdrop that generated visibility around raw materials topics relevant to SUMEX. With the Act drawing increased attention to securing raw material supply sustainably, the session became an impactful platform for highlighting SUMEX's objectives and outputs.

3 EVENT OUTLINES

The following sections introduce the event outline in a nutshell.

Context:

The recently published Critical Raw Materials Act by the European Commission aims to address some of the challenges and opportunities that the EU faces in advancing the energy transition and achieving climate-neutrality by 2050. Among other objectives, it establishes a target of extracting 10% of critical raw materials within

Europe by 2030. It also proposes measures to expedite the permitting process for mining projects and seeks to enhance

And seeks to enhance the monitoring and risk management of supply disruptions while upholding high social and environmental standards for production of critical raw materials.

However, the implementation of this proposed EU regulation faces two major challenges: increasing international competition for mineral raw materials and domestic public opposition to mining and quarrying. This session examined both aspects, seeking an optimal balance between securing the raw materials needed for the green transition in Europe and protecting Europe's natural capital.

Target audience:

The main target audiences for the event were policymakers and authorities involved in land-use planning, environmental conservation and mineral resources extraction. Additionally, the session was designed for NGOs, civil society organisations and academia.

Speakers:

- Thomas Spormans, Permanent Delegation of the European Union to the United Nations Office
- Dumitru Fornea, European Economic and Social Committee / NTUC MERIDIAN Romania
- Linn Andersson, Boliden
- José Miguel Martins, Portuguese Mining Authority
- Julian Hilton, EGRM of United Nations Economic Commission for Europe

Moderator: Katharina Gugerell, University of Natural Resources and Life Sciences, Vienna (BOKU)

Keynote speaker: Michael Tost, Montanuniversität Leoben

Agenda of the Session:

11:00 – 11:05: Welcome and introduction.

11:05 – 11:30: Introduction to Panel / Remarks from participants.

11:30 – 12:25: Panel Discussion among all participants, and Q&A from audience.

12:25 – 12:30 Thank you note and closure.

4 PROMOTION

To broadly advertise the session, a promotional card was created and a dedicated website was set up at <https://www.sumexproject.eu/2023/08/07/sumex-world-resources-forum-2023/> (see Figure 1).

Figure 1: Promotional card for the SUMEX session at the World Resources Forum.

Social media posts were made on a regular basis throughout summer via the LinkedIn, Twitter and Facebook accounts of all projects co-hosting the session.

Figure 2: Examples of social media posts made about the WRF session.

In addition, a dedicated LinkedIn event was created to encourage the LinkedIn community to join the session and ensure higher engagement rates. A total of 136 persons signed up for the event via LinkedIn.

🚩 **SUMEX project, CIRAN Project EU & RE-SOURCING Stakeholder Platform** invite you to a high-level panel discussion:

"Balancing minerals extraction & nature protection: The implications of the EU #CRMA for Europe's energy transition"

📍 **World Resources Forum** - in Geneva 🇨🇭 or online
 📅 05/09/2023 - 11-12:30 CEST
 🔗 <https://lnkd.in/dzwck4jX>

Speakers:

- **Thomas Spoormans**, Permanent Delegation of the European Union to the United Nations Office
- **Dumitru Fornea**, **European Economic and Social Committee** / NTUC MERIDIAN Romania
- **Linn Andersson**, **Boliden**
- **José Miguel Martins**, Portuguese Mining Authority
- **Julian Hilton**, **United Nations Economic Commission for Europe**

Moderator: **Katharina Gugerell**, **University of Natural Resources and Life Sciences, Vienna (BOKU)**

Figure 3: Post about the LinkedIn event.

Furthermore, a LinkedIn advertising campaign ran from August 24th to September 4th 2023, promoting the event to potentially interested stakeholders in a targeted manner. The total budget for this campaign was set at 300€ resulting in 47,178 impressions and 2,070 clicks on the event advertisement.

In combination with two other LinkedIn campaigns for the second live run of the SUMEX MOOC (total campaign budget set to 900€), this contributed to the growth of the number of SUMEX LinkedIn followers. In the last 90 days, the number of followers increased from 309 to 1,757 persons, corresponding to an increase of more than 470%.

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Figure 4: Excerpts from LinkedIn follower, visitor and content impression metrics between 19 June and 16 September.

The advertisement campaigns on LinkedIn accordingly created an enlarged platform for the SUMEX session at the World Resources Forum and any follow-up communications.

5 OUTCOMES AND CONCLUSIONS

In total, the diffusion workshop garnered significant interest, with a participation of over 220 individuals. Approximately 70 attendees joined the in-person discussions held in Geneva, while a substantial online audience of 155 followed the live stream via Zoom. This online viewership encompassed those who registered through the WRF website for either single or multiple-day access to the entire conference and those who opted for free streaming of the SUMEX session, with a total of 217 individuals from 37 different countries registering via Eventbrite.

The recording of the session is available via the SUMEX YouTube channel (<https://youtu.be/B7D2u3CgN7E?feature=shared>). Highlights from the discussion will be extracted and shared across social media channels (see links to SUMEX [Twitter](#), [LinkedIn](#), [Facebook](#)) throughout the month of October.

The main takeaways from the session can be summarised as follows:

1. **Creating a level playing field throughout the entire raw materials value chain:** The workshop underscored the importance of striking a balance between environmental protection goals and ensuring domestic access to and transformation of mineral raw materials in Europe. This equilibrium promotes fair competition across the entire value chain.
2. **Addressing the loss of public trust in the mining industry:** Recognising the erosion of public trust in the mining industry, the session emphasised the imperative of transparency, open access to information, and active stakeholder engagement throughout the mine permitting, extraction, and closure processes.
3. **Improving communication with local communities and policymakers:** Stressing the significance of improving communication with local communities and policymakers, particularly by better distinguishing between the stages of exploration and extraction to address concerns more precisely.
4. **Enhancing the trackability and traceability of mineral raw materials:** Ensuring the traceability of mineral raw materials throughout the production cycle and curbing illegal resource movements were identified as key challenges that need to be effectively addressed.
5. **Taking into consideration energy consumption challenges:** The workshop acknowledged the need for affordable access to renewable energy sources across the entire value chain to reduce carbon emissions and promote European production.
6. **Moving towards a circular economy:** The transition towards a circular economy featured prominently, with an emphasis on policy-level actions to promote the use of secondary raw materials through recycling.
7. **Questioning growth paradigms:** The session prompted reflection on the necessity of mineral extraction, aligning it with sufficiency considerations and integrating these aspects into circular economy policies.

In his closing words, SUMEX project coordinator Michael Tost emphasised that two out of the three organising projects are about to end, i.e. SUMEX and RE-SOURCING are approaching their conclusions. SUMEX aims at providing recommendations for policy and industry concerning the Critical Raw Materials Act, but also in general on how to promote the transition of the raw material sector towards sustainability.

Simultaneously, SUMEX aims to hand over the baton to the CIRAN project Specifically addresses the question of finding a balance between nature protection and the need to access mineral raw materials.

Last but not least, participants were invited to join the [SUMEX Community of Practice \(CoP\) on LinkedIn](#). This discussion group aims to offer a virtual forum on LinkedIn for continuous discussions on sustainable management in the extractive industries, both during and beyond the project’s funding period. It was agreed to post open questions from the audience which could not be addressed during the live session due to time constraints, within the CoP to allow for follow up discussions.

To close the session, participants both onsite and online were invited to share feedback on the session. Overall, participating respondents concurred that the session:

- Provided them with a better problem understanding in the transition to a sustainable extractive industry sector,
- Provided them with ideas for the next steps to support the transition to sustainable extraction,
- Supported the exchange of information and the common understanding of sustainable supply.

This is illustrated in Figure 5.

Balancing minerals extraction & nature protection

Figure 5: Feedback from event participants on the relevance of the session.

when asked about the meaning of sustainability the majority of the survey participants cited the words “responsibility” and “efficiency”, both being closely related to the main session takeaways mentioned above.

What does sustainability mean to you?

35 Responses

Figure 6: Answers from event attendees who replied to the question “What does sustainability mean to you?”

6 Annex 1: TRANSCRIPT OF THE SESSION

SUMEX Project background

SUMEX is a 36-months project funded by the EC starting on 01.11.2020. Its primary goal is to establish a European sustainability framework aimed at improving the permitting procedure throughout the extractive value chain (which includes prospecting, exploration, extraction, processing, closure and post-closure activities). This framework seeks to ensure timely decisions, a transparent governmental regulatory regime, favourable financial and administrative conditions and sustainable natural environmental and social conditions. The main mission of SUMEX is to assist policymakers and other stakeholders in seizing this opportunity.

To foster more, but sustainable mineral production in the EU, SUMEX (*SU*stainable *M*anagement in *EX*tractive industries) will establish a sustainability framework for the extractive industry in Europe. It does so by considering the Sustainable Development Goals, the European Green Deal, as well as EU Social License to Operate considerations and will involve stakeholders from industry, government, academia and civil society backgrounds from all across the EU.

The framework will be applied across the extractive value chain to analyze mineral, economic, environmental, and social policy frameworks at the EU, member state, and selected regional levels.

This analysis will encompass five focus areas: socio-economic and environmental impact assessments, land use planning, health and safety, reporting official statistics, and permitting processes/policy integration. SUMEX aims to identify or develop, where necessary, good practices and tools for an open-access toolkit. This toolkit will form the basis for a broader Community of Practice (CoP) and capacity-building efforts.

The CoP will engage relevant stakeholder groups, with a specific focus on permitting authorities across the EU. It will provide a digital platform and host a series of workshops and webinars. In SUMEX, the knowledge and experience gained from previous projects lay a strong foundation for addressing the challenge of effectively integrating sustainability considerations throughout the entire raw materials value chain.

Challenge: No common understanding of sustainable management in extractive industries

SUMEX supports the set-up of a European sustainability framework to improve the permitting procedure along the extractive value chain (prospecting, exploration, extraction, processing, closure, post closure activities), to guarantee timely decisions, a transparent governmental regulatory regime, appealing financial and administrative conditions and sustainable natural environmental and social conditions. The main mission of SUMEX is to assist policymakers and other stakeholders in seizing this opportunity.

Objectives of SUMEX

- Strengthen policy coordination and agenda setting along the mineral extraction value chain;
- Propose a uniform EU sustainable management in extractive industries context;
- Cluster with other projects to identify good practices and good practise principles;
- Identify good practises and principles for policy strategies and strategic approaches, coordination/integration and approaches and property rights regimes for different institutional systems;
- Build a toolkit with good practises, with a focus on access to land, permitting and policy coordination and integration;
- Identify stakeholder learning needs and requirements;
- Deploy an open access toolkit for capacity building across EU and with all stakeholders.

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More info on <https://www.sumexproject.eu/>

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